

SOCIAL SCIENCES

PERSONNEL DEVELOPMENT MANAGEMENT IN THE CONDITIONS OF GLOBALIZATION OF KNOWLEDGE AND TRANSFORMATION OF THE SCIENTIFIC SPACE

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Abstract

The article analyzes key aspects of the transformation of the scientific environment that affect the requirements for personnel, in particular digitalization, international mobility and interdisciplinarity. It is noted that the development of adaptive, flexible models of professional development aimed at individual growth trajectories and active international cooperation is important. The main components of personnel development management have been identified, including career planning, competency assessment, mentoring, and the implementation of modern digital tools to improve performance. Practical recommendations include creating conditions for continuous professional development, supporting international mobility, and developing partnerships, which contributes to increasing the competitiveness of scientific and educational institutions at the global level.

Keywords: personnel development, knowledge globalization, human resource policy, digitalization, academic mobility.

Problem Statement. In today's conditions of globalization and increased international competition, human capital is becoming increasingly important as a key factor in ensuring sustainable development and innovative progress. Along with the development of digital technologies, openness of scientific research, and increasing mobility of personnel, new challenges arise that require the adaptation of personnel development management systems. This is especially true for the fields of education, science, and research, where traditional approaches to training and professional growth do not meet the requirements of a rapidly changing global environment. In this regard, there is a need to update methods of managing personnel development, implement new training strategies, adapt to the conditions of open science, interdisciplinary and mobility, which will allow to effectively maintain intellectual potential and promote innovative development in the context of global competition. This also requires the creation of flexible, inclusive and future-oriented learning and development models that can respond quickly to changes in the external environment, ensuring the training of highly qualified personnel for the global scientific and educational space. In addition, it is important to integrate the latest technologies into the educational process, which will better meet the needs of the modern labor market and ensure the sustainable development of the intellectual community.

Analysis of Research and Publications. In scientific discourse, attention is growing to the problem of managing personnel development in the context of globalization of knowledge, digitalization, and internationalization of the scientific environment. In particular, studies [1-2] focus on the potential of digital technologies to stimulate independent learning among academics, which contributes to personalized professional growth in the context of the digital transformation of

education, and emphasize the importance of developing digital competencies among teachers and researchers. In this context, scientists [3] propose innovative approaches to teacher training, in particular, emphasizing the development of creativity, the introduction of modern educational technologies, and the use of flexible learning formats that also meet the requirements of the digital transformation of the educational process.

At the same time, as noted in [4-5], the development of educational institutions is impossible without optimizing personnel policy, which should be based on effective planning, the formation of a sustainable educational environment, and the strengthening of human capital. A separate role in this process is played by motivational support for personnel, which is an important element for ensuring staff stability and promoting their professional growth in the context of socio-economic transformations.

Modern approaches to strategic management of personnel development in the context of the transformation of the educational environment, proposed by scientists [6-7], involve the development of personnel management tools that take into account the dynamic transformation of the educational environment, growing requirements for the quality of education, and constant changes in the regulatory environment.

Scientists also pay significant attention to issues of international staff mobility, which is one of the key factors in increasing the competitiveness of academic staff, facilitating their participation in global research initiatives [8]. At the same time, this process is accompanied not only by positive results, such as obtaining new knowledge, but also by challenges, in particular, by the outflow of personnel, which requires the development of a balanced personnel policy to optimize these processes [9].

The scientific achievements of the above authors indicate that rethinking models of personnel development management in the context of globalization of knowledge and transformation of the scientific space remains a relevant task, particularly in the context of challenges associated with the digitalization and internationalization of the scientific environment. This opens up new prospects for further research and development of new approaches aimed at supporting and preserving scientific potential in Ukraine.

Purpose of the Article. The purpose of the article is to form the components of a comprehensive approach to managing personnel development in the context of the globalization of knowledge and the transformation of the scientific space, as well as to provide practical recommendations and relevant tools aimed at improving the personnel management system in scientific and educational institutions.

Main Text. In the context of knowledge globalization and the transformation of the scientific space, there is a growing need to rethink approaches to personnel development management in the academic and educational sphere. Building an innovative, mobile, and adaptive workforce is becoming a critically important task to ensure the competitiveness of national science and education. This necessity arises not only from dynamic changes in the system of knowledge generation and dissemination but also from the increasing role of human capital as a key resource for the intellectual development of society. Under such conditions, a strategic priority is to create an environment that fosters professional growth, academic mobility, lifelong learning, and effective engagement of personnel in innovative activities. Personnel development management must respond to new challenges, including digitalization, the internationalization of scientific processes, and the demands of transdisciplinary collaboration, which calls for both theoretical rethinking and practical modernization of traditional human resource models.

Managing personnel development primarily requires understanding the essence and transformation of this concept in the academic and educational environment, which is undergoing significant changes under the influence of the transition to a knowledge-based economy. The evolution of approaches to personnel development from traditional administrative personnel management to strategic human capital management is reflected in many scientific studies. In particular, Becker G. emphasizes the importance of education and professional skills as a form of investment in human capital [10], and Drucker P. defines knowledge as a key resource of a post-industrial society [11]. In the fields of science and education, personnel development has specific features associated with continuous knowledge updating, participation in interdisciplinary projects and international cooperation. These factors, in turn, shape the quality of human capital in education, which determines the intellectual potential of the nation and its overall competitiveness [12]. At the same time, globalization processes are transforming the functional structure of HR management in the scientific sphere, shifting the focus from administrative support to the facilitation of

academic mobility, knowledge transfer, and the development of a creative environment [13-14].

The globalization of knowledge significantly transforms the requirements for academic and educational staff, in particular, requiring their adaptation to new working conditions, academic interaction, and the digital environment. Among the main trends determining these changes, scientists identify such factors as open access to scientific information, internationalization of educational programs, and interdisciplinary integration of research [15].

The transformation of the scientific environment, which acts as a system-forming factor, requires a rethinking of approaches to managing personnel development in the academic and educational spheres. Among the key aspects of this transformation, scientists highlight [16]:

- digitalization of science and education: changing traditional formats of work organization and implementing open science tools, digital research platforms, analytical services, and knowledge management systems;
- new requirements for academic and teaching staff include the need to master data processing tools, visualize research results, and communicate effectively in online environments;
- personnel adaptability is the ability to quickly adapt to changing working and learning conditions in a digital environment;
- working in digital project and network teams requires developing collaboration skills in digital and interdisciplinary projects;
- development of management and communication competencies: improving the level of management and communication skills for effective work in a modern scientific environment.

In modern personnel management in science, the principles of systematicity, adaptability, result orientation, and continuous improvement are of priority. These principles ensure effective management of personnel development in the conditions of constant changes in the scientific and educational environment. The main functional components of the personnel management system are career planning, competency assessment, mentoring organization, and development of individual learning and professional realization trajectories that contribute to the formation of highly qualified scientific personnel [17].

Given the complexity and multidimensional nature of the changes taking place in the scientific and educational environment, there is a growing need for the application of a comprehensive approach to personnel development management, which, in our opinion, encompasses the following key components:

- evolution of the concept of «personnel development»: taking into account the shift in understanding development as a continuous, competence-oriented, and individualized process of professional growth for employees in education and science;
- impact of knowledge globalization: recognizing new demands on staff, including the need

for digital literacy, interdisciplinarity, academic mobility, and the ability to operate within a global information space;

- transformation of the scientific environment: adaptation to new forms of organizing research activities, digitalization of communication processes, and the growing role of inter-institutional and international cooperation;

- current state of personnel policy in Ukraine: analysis of existing problems and barriers, including insufficient funding, brain drain, lack of incentives for professional development, and a low level of strategic planning;

- theoretical and methodological foundations for improving personnel policy: formulation of principles of flexibility, adaptability, strategic management, mentorship support, and leadership potential development;

- practical implementation mechanisms: introduction of systems for competency monitoring, individualized educational trajectories, internal professional development programs, support for international mobility, and development of partnership networks.

The proposed approach to personnel development management is comprehensive in nature, as it combines theoretical and methodological foundations with practical mechanisms, taking into account both external

global determinants and internal features of the functioning of the scientific and educational sphere. Its implementation involves a systematic rethinking of personnel policy based on the principles of flexibility, innovation, strategic orientation, and sustainable development. This creates a foundation for the effective formation, retention, and enhancement of human capital and increases the competitiveness of scientific and educational institutions amid transformational changes.

Among the key areas for improving the personnel development management system in scientific and educational institutions, four strategic blocks of measures should be highlighted: the implementation of systems for monitoring competencies and staff performance; the creation of conditions for continuous professional development; the development of partnerships and support for international mobility; and the updating of institutional human resource strategies. Each of these directions includes specific tools, such as digital competency profiles, individual development plans, academic exchange programs, performance indicators (KPIs), personnel analytics platforms, internal training activities, and the revision of regulatory documentation. The expected outcomes include the enhancement of staff professional potential, strengthening of the human resource pool, increased institutional flexibility, and improved competitiveness of institutions in the global academic space. A structured presentation of these approaches is provided in Table 1.

Table 1

Tools and Mechanisms for Strengthening Strategic Areas of Human Resource Development

Strategic Area of HR Development Enhancement	Tools and Mechanisms
Implementation of systems for monitoring personnel competencies and performance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of digital competency profiles for employees • Utilization of comprehensive assessment tools (360-degree feedback, professional competency maps) • Design and implementation of performance indicators (KPIs) for academic and research staff • Analysis of personnel development dynamics using digital analytics platforms (e.g., Power BI, TalentSoft)
Creating conditions for continuous professional development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of Individual Development Plans (IDPs) • Organization of internal educational programs: trainings, seminars, workshops, and mentoring sessions • Access to external online platforms (Prometheus, Coursera, edX) for professional upskilling • Development of a corporate culture of learning and self-development
Development of partnerships and support for international mobility of researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conclusion of academic cooperation agreements with universities and research institutions in the EU and other regions • Participation in international grant programs (e.g., Erasmus+, Horizon Europe, COST, etc.) • Support for academic exchange programs, internships, and scientific visits • Encouragement of co-authored publications with foreign colleagues and participation in international conferences
Updating the human resource strategy of educational and research institutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Revision of internal regulatory documents in line with the principles of sustainable personnel development • Enhancement of workforce planning based on risk analysis and forecasting of employment structure changes • Creation of conditions for attracting young researchers and supporting them during the stage of professional adaptation

The application of the proposed recommendations will ensure a systematic renewal of human resource policies, improve the quality of human capital management, and contribute to enhancing the competitiveness of the scientific and educational environment in the face of global challenges.

Conclusions. The conducted research has shown that effective personnel development management in the scientific and educational sphere requires a reconsideration of traditional HR approaches, taking into account globalization challenges, digital transformation, and shifts in the structure of scientific knowledge. Within a comprehensive framework, it has been substantiated that the key conditions for the sustainable development of human capital include: the systemic nature of managerial decisions, adaptability to institutional changes, a focus on developing innovative competencies, and support for professional mobility.

It has been established that the globalization of knowledge significantly transforms personnel requirements, highlighting the need for digital literacy, interdisciplinary collaboration, and openness to international cooperation. The transformation of the scientific space necessitates the development of new models of professional growth based on the principles of lifelong learning, flexible educational pathways, and the use of digital knowledge management platforms.

Based on the analysis of theoretical and methodological foundations and practical challenges, the key directions for improving human resource policy have been identified. These include the implementation of competency and performance monitoring systems, the development of mentoring mechanisms, the support of international mobility, and the creation of conditions for personalized professional growth.

Therefore, personnel development management in the context of knowledge globalization and scientific transformation should be grounded in the integration of strategic vision, digital tools, inter-institutional cooperation, and a focus on the qualitative renewal of human capital as a foundation for the innovative capacity of scientific and educational institutions.

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